

An Analysis of the Relationship between EMDR, Panic Attacks and Anxiety

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Abstract

In the literature, there are many randomized controlled studies (RCT) and studies on the effectiveness of eye movement desensitization and reprocessing (EMDR) therapy for adults with anxiety disorders. Three RCTs focusing on panic disorder with or without agoraphobia (PDA); While two studies targeted specific phobias, the dependent variable of another RCT was “self-esteem,” which was considered a mediating factor for anxiety disorders. In four RCTs, EMDR therapy showed a positive effect on panic and phobic symptoms, while one RCT on PDA was partially negative, and one study failed to improve self-esteem in patients with anxiety disorders. Taken as a whole, these preliminary data suggest that EMDR therapy may be effective not only for PD but also for certain phobias. Further controlled studies are needed to confirm these findings and to systematically evaluate the efficacy of EMDR therapy for generalized anxiety disorder, social anxiety and agoraphobia. Because cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) is currently considered first-line therapy for anxiety disorders, controlled comparisons between EMDR therapy and CBT will be particularly useful in future investigations of EMDR therapy of anxiety disorders. Eye movement desensitization and reprocessing (EMDR) is an integrative psychotherapy that has been extensively evaluated in its approach to trauma and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). In summary, the AIP model is based on the idea that the neurobiological system naturally tries to process existing perceptions in a way that promotes associations with relevant stored information, facilitates learning, and relieves emotional distress. Consequently, the transfer of information from implicit memory systems to explicit memory systems (Shapiro 2001) allows for the resolution of disturbing thoughts, emotions, and bodily sensations by facilitating access to the stored material and associating it with more coherent information. However, the intense impact and subsequent dissociation that accompanies trauma can interfere with this process and cause dysfunctional storage of information (for example, images, thoughts, emotions, and sensations) in the memory network.

Keywords: *EMDR, Panic Attack, Anxiety, Psychological Disorders, Psychological Disorders Relationship*

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1. Introduction

isolated in the event network , associations with adaptive information are a preventable phenomenon. In this case, the unresolved phenomenon can easily be triggered during similar encounters. Often this leads to intrusive thoughts, feelings, and somatic responses. The resulting habitual response patterns can be manifested in characterological difficulties, psychopathology, and avoidance behaviors associated with phobias and panic disorders (Shapiro 2001, 2002). The ability of EMDR to access and target an etiological conditioning event is appreciated. (“emdria.omeka.net”) It is also possible to address past, present and future symptoms in the absence of a known etiological event. (“EMDR TREATMENT OF PANIC DISORDER WITH AGORAPHOBIA: CASE REPORT”) Therefore, EMDR can address panic and phobia regardless of the method by which the symptoms or fear are acquired.

Once appropriate targets are selected, the EMDR protocol considers all experiential components (images, thoughts, emotions, bodily sensations) to activate the information processing system as described by the AIP model (Shapiro 2001, 2002). EMDR was introduced, for example, in Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH) in 1998, just three years after the war (1992-1995). Thus, appropriately trained mental health workers began using EMDR therapies in daily assistance to BiH citizens in need (Trlin & Hasanoviü 2018, Hasanoviü et al. 2021). The aim of this study is to present how EMDR therapy is used to successfully address panic disorder with agoraphobia.

Panic disorder is associated with possible anxiety that follows recurrent severe anxiety states (for example, anticipatory anxiety). Panic attacks usually occur after a highly stressful period of life and are often associated with personal or death or family illness, separations or other difficulties in interpersonal relationships (Gordeev, 2008; Markowitz, Weissman, Ouellette, Lish, & Klerman, 1989). PD can occur with or without agoraphobia (PDA), a fear of being in places or situations that are difficult to escape from or embarrassing. The agoraphobic person avoids many situations and therefore limits their social and work life. The treatment of panic disorder has traditionally consisted of PD treatments with or without agoraphobia,

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pharmacological and cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) approaches, both of which have been considered effective (Sturpe & Weissman, 2002).

According to the 2007 National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence (NICE) guidelines, the most effective treatment for PD was expressed as CBT, with significant reduction in post-treatment symptoms and sustained success at 6-month follow-up (Galassi, Quercioli, Charismas, Niccolai & Barciulli, 2007). Furthermore, complete resolution of symptoms in 75% of cases has been reported following 12 sessions of treatment, with greater efficacy of CBT than long-term pharmacological treatment using the anxiolytic Alprazolam (Kahn, van Praag, Wetzler, Asnis, & Barr, 1988; Ost, Thulin, & Ramnerö, 2004).

Some studies (Gould, Otto, & Pollack, 1995; Otto & Whittal, 1995) have shown that relatively “short” CBT therapy (12 sessions) can completely reduce symptoms in 75% of cases, with results being better for patients using CBT. CBT is higher than those on long-term drug therapy. Results from a study of 76 patients with Parkinson's disease, with or without agoraphobia, found that a combination of cognitive techniques (psychoeducation, cognitive restructuring, and problem solving) and behavioral modalities (interoceptive and in vivo exposure) was effective in remission of acute seizures. Maintaining success for up to 6 months after symptoms and treatment is a separate study (Galassi et al., 2007). In 1990, psychologist Francine Shapiro developed a new type of psychotherapy known as Eye Movement Desensitization and Reprocessing, or EMDR.

2. EMDR Therapy, Anxiety and Panic Attack Relationship

EMDR therapy is an effective treatment option for people suffering from anxiety, panic, PTSD or trauma. More work is of course needed to summarize this situation to get past your past. According to the EMDR Research Foundation, EMDR has been clinically validated (the gold standard for clinical research) by more than 30 randomized, controlled trials. (“EMDR Therapy for Anxiety, Panic, PTSD and Trauma”) EMDR is an integrative psychotherapy approach that has been extensively researched and proven effective in trauma treatment. EMDR therapy

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includes a set of standardized protocols that combine elements from many different treatment approaches and alleviate psychological trauma for millions of people of all ages.

3. What is EMDR?

EMDR therapy is a gradual, focused approach to treating trauma and other symptoms by safely and deliberately reconnecting the traumatized person to trauma-related images, self-thoughts, emotions, and body sensations and allowing the trauma's natural healing powers. Moving the brain towards adaptive resolution is a separate definition. It is based on the idea that symptoms occur when trauma and other negative or challenging experiences overwhelm the brain's natural ability to heal, and that the healing process can be facilitated and completed through dual stimulation as the client re-experiences the trauma in context. (“Trauma: What is it? - Mood Psychotherapy & Coaching”) The safe environment of the therapist's office (dual awareness) makes this process more dependable. “Identifies and addresses traumatic experiences that exceed the brain's natural coping capacity and ultimately create traumatic symptoms such as flashbacks or anxiety, or harmful coping strategies such as isolation behavior and self-medication with alcohol or drugs.”

a. How EMDR Works

Through EMDR, individuals safely reprocess traumatic information until it is no longer psychologically destructive to their life. Over time, exposure to traumatic memories no longer causes negative emotions and bothersome symptoms.

EMDR has eight phases:

The technique, which, if attached, turns into a negative memory, teaches the person to change their view of themselves by learning to associate it with a positive belief instead. (“EMDR Therapy for Anxiety, Panic, PTSD and Trauma”) For example, it is common for victims of abuse to feel that they “deserve” the abuse. EMDR helps the person see this as a self-destructive thought. All sensations and emotions associated with memory are identified. The person then

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reviews the memory while focusing on an external stimulus that produces rapid (or bilateral) eye movement. Typically, this is done by watching the therapist move two fingers. (“EMDR Therapy for Anxiety, Panic, PTSD and Trauma”) After each set of bilateral movements (usually involving both eyes), the individual is asked how they are feeling.

The chosen positive belief is then "inserted" through dual action to replace the negative belief. Sessions usually last one hour. When a difficult/traumatic memory gets stuck, it prevents the brain from properly processing and storing that memory. During EMDR, individuals process memory securely, which leads to a peaceful resolution. The experience results in increased insight into both previously disturbing events and negative thoughts about themselves resulting from the original traumatic event.

b. Who Is EMDR Suitable For?

EMDR therapy is approved by the American Psychiatric Association and the International Association for the Study of Traumatic Stress. Overseas agencies including the United States Department of Veterans Affairs (VA), the Department of Defense and the United Kingdom Department of Health, and Israel's National Mental Health Council have also approved this treatment . According to the EMDR Research Foundation, this includes rape and sexual abuse, war trauma, childhood trauma and neglect, life-threatening accidents and anxiety, depression and substance abuse.

- i. *“What the technique does is change the way we process the presence of physical, emotional and psychological effects, particularly associated with a traumatic event”;*
- ii. *“The sense of pain and danger carried in the self after a traumatic event grips the soul so intensely that it leads to a feeling of being in an emotional quagmire. EMDR works to neutralize belief systems, also known as cognition, and while modifying negative cognition through a series of lateral eye movements, touch, or sound, the client is asked to create the picture of pain and danger (trauma) that bothers them most.*

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” (*“Top Benefits of the EMDR Therapy Process - Foundations Counseling”*)

Does EMDR Therapy Really Work? According to the EMDR Institute, Inc., some research on this type of therapy shows that 84-90% of single trauma survivors no longer have PTSD after just three 90-minute sessions. Another study funded by HMO Kaiser Permanente found that 100% of single trauma survivors and 77% of multiple trauma survivors were no longer diagnosed with PTSD after just six 50-minute sessions.

What's also different about this type of therapeutic intervention is that the therapist doesn't just talk to the client as they go through the process. It is not unusual for sleep to be affected following an EMDR session. Vivid dreams are common, as well as feeling more sensitive to interactions with others and external stimuli. (“Eye Movement Desensitization and Reprocessing - Elaine Freeman CBT”) EMDR Therapy is not the only form of therapy suitable for people dealing with anxiety, PTSD, panic and/or trauma. EMDR therapy is often conducted in conjunction with other forms of therapy.

Taking a comprehensive history revealed that those who contributed to the experience played a crucial role in the development of the condition. Therefore, eye movement desensitization and reprocessing (EMDR) has been used to address early traumatic events, as well as current stimuli that cause discomfort and have persisted in its symptomatology for the past 12 years. "During EMDR processing, the client demonstrated emotional and cognitive changes consistent with trauma resolution, insight, and personal growth." (“EMDR in the Treatment of Panic Disorder With Agoraphobia: A Case ...”) The patient gradually adopted new functional behaviors spontaneously as treatment developed. The therapeutic process and goals are explained in detail. For no apparent reason, your heart starts racing, you sweat, your chest hurts, and breathing seems difficult or impossible.

4. Panic Attack or panic disorder

Panic attack or panic disorder is a type of anxiety disorder. Anxiety disorders are very treatable conditions using psychotherapy. Panic attacks are sudden attacks of intense fear or distress, often accompanied by physical sensations. These feelings are real and can be measured like rapid heart rate. These episodes last for a few minutes and may occur in a particular place, time, or day, or without known signs or warnings. People who have panic attacks often worry that they will happen again, which can make the situation worse. It can be like a giant snowball because the worry of having an attack can create an attack. Sometimes people begin to avoid everyday places or situations for fear or anxiety that another attack will occur. This condition can be mild or profoundly serious, causing significant difficulties in relationships, employment or life satisfaction. CBT (cognitive behavioral therapy) has traditionally been the most effective treatment for panic attacks; however, EMDR research has shown that it is as effective as CBT and can significantly reduce the frequency of panic attacks than CBT (Horst, et.al. 2017).

EMDR (eye movement desensitization and reprocessing) is an evidence-based, non-traditional psychotherapy that can be used to treat panic disorder or anxiety. During EMDR, the client will explore thoughts, feelings, sensations, and self-beliefs related to or associated with a negative event or negative cognition. The therapist will guide the client either by using eye movements back and forth or by using dual movement (touch, lights, sounds). While it is not necessary to verbalize all the details of the negative experience, the client will remember the associated images or events during processing. EMDR is thought to be effective in desensitizing and reprocessing negative events and beliefs because a client can explore them in a comfortable and safe environment with a therapist. CBT (cognitive behavioral therapy) is another evidence-based psychotherapy approach to treating panic disorder and anxiety and is a traditional and intensive research method. CBT uses talk therapy to identify and explore the connections of thoughts, behaviors, and emotions. CBT aims to correct the irrational thinking error and identify the antecedents of undesirable behavior to shape actions into desired behaviors, and it explores emotions and feelings. CBT may use relaxation training to improve coping skills and exposure techniques to gradually increase a person's ability to withstand a feared place or object or overcome fear or anxiety. There is an element of desensitization when investigating fear or anxiety with EMDR therapy for panic attacks. In EMDR, this is mostly non-verbal exploration

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of experiences, sensations, or cognitions while safe in the therapist's office. (“EMDR Therapy for Panic Attacks - AM Nelson”) In CBT, this may be imaginary or actual exposure to identified triggers or cues for fear or anxiety. EMDR is comparable to CBT for the treatment of panic disorders.

Sometimes choosing EMDR therapy for panic attacks can be a client's preference or comfort level. If so, CBT may be speech therapy for you. Other clients experience intense emotional reactions when talking about their fears, anxieties, or concerns, or have already tried talk therapy approaches. Three RCTs focusing on panic disorder with or without agoraphobia (PDA); While two studies targeted specific phobias, the dependent variable of another RCT is “self-esteem,” which is considered a mediating factor for anxiety disorders.

In four RCTs, EMDR therapy showed a positive effect on panic and phobic symptoms, while one RCT on PDA was partially negative, and one study failed to improve self-esteem in patients with anxiety disorders. Taken as a whole, these preliminary data suggest that EMDR therapy may be effective not only for PD but also for certain phobias. Further controlled studies are needed to confirm these findings and to systematically evaluate the efficacy of EMDR therapy for generalized anxiety disorder, social anxiety and agoraphobia. As cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) is currently considered first-line therapy for anxiety disorders, controlled comparisons between EMDR therapy and CBT will be particularly useful in future investigations of EMDR therapy of anxiety disorders.

Eye Movement Desensitization and Reprocessing (EMDR), a promising new technique for the treatment of traumatic memories, was evaluated in a pilot study. The subjects were seven clients suffering from panic disorder and had received EMDR treatment for memories of the past and anticipated panic attacks and other anxiety-provoking memories of self-interest. Standardized self-report inventories and behavioral monitoring tools were used to measure change with treatment. After EMDR, subjects reported a significant reduction in the frequency of panic attacks, fear of experiencing panic attacks, general anxiety, thoughts about negative consequences of experiencing anxiety, fear of body sensations, depression, and other pathology measures.

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5. Literature Examples

Raskin, Peeke, Dikman, and Pinker (1982) reviewed the antecedents of anxiety disorders and found that 53% of participants with panic disorder experienced death, divorce, or other separation from their parents during childhood or adolescence. These findings also showed that the impact of traumatic life events depended on the age at which they occurred. Brown, Harris, and Eales (1993) confirmed the impact of abandonment and separation on the development of panic disorders, adding that exposure to unpredictable and uncontrollable stimuli in childhood may also contribute to such symptoms. (“EMDR TREATMENT OF PANIC DISORDER WITH AGORAPHOBIA: CASE REPORT”) These results are consistent with AIP theory (Shapiro 2001, 2002) because these events may have caused enough distress to impair information processing of the event, resulting in the stored effects and sensations that underlie the pathology. Although most people agree that the intensity of a traumatic event contributes to the impact on the individual, the participants' mental processing skills should also be considered. For example, an event that is harmless for an adult may be traumatic for a child. According to the AIP model, these events are considered minor T traumas, but events required to diagnose PTSD, such as accidents and natural disasters, are considered major T traumas (Shapiro 2001, 2002).

As mentioned earlier, if the neurologic structure of the adult is still affected by the traces of an insufficiently processed traumatic childhood experience, a neutral current event may be experienced by the participant as suffering and elicit an intense anxiety response. The relationship between symptoms and previous negative or stressful experiences is particularly clear in panic disorders. (“EMDR TREATMENT OF PANIC DISORDER WITH AGORAPHOBIA: CASE REPORT”) In fact, regarding the role of unpleasant events in the etiology and maintenance of emotional distress, memory plays a mediating role between the event and psychopathology (Williams 1996).

Therefore, working on negative and damaging experiences is considered the key to accessing and changing dysfunctional information and behaviors. Given the proven effectiveness of

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EMDR in this regard, it can be expected to effectively address traumatic etiological events related to panic disorders. However, before using EMDR, therapists should take a thorough client history to identify and describe experiences that create vulnerability to these symptoms. The therapeutic goal is to identify the moment and condition responsible for the dysfunction. The primary focus of EMDR therapy is the processing of etiological events, triggers and new behaviors within the session. Targeting individual memories often leads to insights and uncovering other triggers and events for further processing .

Apparently, EMDR provides direct access to the memory network and allows previous memories to be metabolized. The sequence of treatment procedures shown in the present case is especially important. The AIP model guiding EMDR therapy suggests that this dysfunction is primarily generated by dysfunctionally stored memories and is best treated with direct targeting. It is assumed that the anxiety and fear felt by the client are the emotions and physical sensations inherent in the implicit memory network (Shapiro 2001). Therefore, the processing of etiological events that cause and maintain dysfunction is the most important aspect of EMDR therapy. In vivo exposure is recommended only after the etiologic events have been processed and the fear has largely resolved. Subsequent in vivo exposure is used to reveal specific triggers or co-targets that need to be processed. As noted in this situation, clients often spontaneously stop avoiding and begin to exhibit new positive behaviors following EMDR processing.

6. Panic Disorder Treatment with or Without Agoraphobia

Before determining the appropriate targets for EMDR Therapy in the treatment of panic disorder with or without agoraphobia, it is important to determine whether the client has panic attacks and whether they meet the DSM-5 (American Psychiatric Association, 2013) criteria for panic disorder. Panic attacks are repetitive and unexpected and involve a surge within minutes that can range from intense discomfort to extreme fear.

They are accompanied by at least four or more of the following physiological symptoms:

- i. *paresthesias (tingling or numbness);*

- ii. *feeling of heat or chills;*
- iii. *experiences dizziness, drowsiness, unsteadiness, or weakness;*
- iv. *nausea or abdominal discomfort;*
- v. *chest pain or distress; a feeling of suffocation;*
- vi. *shortness of breath or a feeling of suffocation;*
- vii. *tremors or tremors;*
- viii. *exude; and fast or irregular heartbeat.*
- ix. *There are also intense cognitive distortions such as unreality (derealization) or self-detachment (depersonalization); (“PANIC DISORDER AND AGORAPHOBIA EMDR Therapy Protocol for ... - ResearchGate”)*
- x. *fear of going crazy or losing control; and/or fear of dying.*
- xi.

To meet the criteria, a person must either constantly have another panic attack or worry about the consequences (losing control, have a nervous breakdown, etc.), or must change behavior significantly during the period to avoid another panic attack.

Panic disorder is not diagnosed if the symptoms can be attributed to the physiological effects of a substance (such as medication or drug use) or another medical condition (such as heart disorders or hyperthyroidism) or another mental disorder (such as social anxiety disorder or specific phobia).

Agoraphobia is characterized by fear of being in closed or open spaces, queuing or being in crowds, being alone outside the home, or using public transport. These situations are difficult because panic Fear, the fear that escape may be difficult and help may not be available, predominates leading to avoidance of these situations or needing the presence of another person. The fear or anxiety felt is disproportionate to the actual situation itself; this includes the occurrence of another medical condition. Such fear, anxiety, or avoidance lasts 6 months or longer, impairs social, occupational, or other functioning, and is not explained by other mental disorders. EMDR (Eye Movement Desensitization and Reprocessing) is a form of

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psychotherapy developed by Francine Shapiro in 1987 to assist people with Post Traumatic Stress Disorder.

EMDR is driven by the Adaptive Computing model (Shapiro 2007). The Adaptive Information Processing model believes that PTSD and other disorder symptoms (unless biologically caused) are the result of distress from past traumatic experiences where memory was not adequately processed. These unresolved memories are believed to include thoughts, beliefs, emotions, and physical sensations that occurred during the event.

When these memories are repeated or triggered by a reminder, the initial effect of the event is re-experienced as symptoms of PTSD or other disorders. Unlike other types of therapy that focus on the cognitive and behavioral aspects of trauma, such as identifying and successfully addressing the beliefs, thoughts, feelings, and general behaviors that result from traumatic events, EMDR focuses solely on memory. It is theorized that changing the way memory is stored in the brain will reduce and eliminate symptoms triggered by unprocessed memories. EMDR attempts to resolve these raw memories through an eight-step process:

- i. *Stage 1: History taking*
- ii. *Stage 2: Preparing the Client*
- iii. *Stage 3: Evaluation of target memory*
- iv. *Stage 4-7: Processing memory for adaptive resolution*
- v. *Stage 8: Evaluation of treatment results*

This process is typically offered in eight to twelve sessions (depending on the results). The EMDR Institute briefly describes the overall process as follows:

"Eye movements (or other bilateral stimulation) are used during part of the session." ("Techniques | mysite") After determining which memory to target first, the clinician asks the client to keep various aspects of that event or thought in mind and using their eyes to watch the therapist's hand move back and forth in the client's field of vision. As this happens, internal associations arise and clients begin to process memory and disturbing emotions, for reasons that a Harvard researcher believes are linked to the biological mechanisms involved in Rapid Eye Movement (REM) sleep.

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In successful EMDR therapy, the meaning of painful events is transformed on an emotional level. For example, a rape survivor moves from feelings of fear and self-loathing to embracing the firm belief that "I'm out of this and I'm stronger." Unlike talk therapy, the insights clients gain in EMDR therapy derive from the client's own accelerated intellectual and emotional processes rather than the clinician's interpretation. The net effect is that clients feel empowered by EMDR therapy by experiences that once humiliated them.

Since its inception, therapists have used EMDR for several other purposes, including depression, anxiety disorder, sexual dysfunction, schizophrenia, eating disorders, and even psychological stress from other medical conditions. There are both strong advocates of EMDR and those who say that EMDR is ineffective overall. People who have received EMDR report mixed results, from helpful to making things worse. Some of the latest research shows that EMDR can provide positive clinical outcomes in trauma treatment; however, more research is needed because previous research has shown limitations, including long-term efficacy. ("EMDR For Anxiety Disorder and Panic Attacks - AnxietyCentre.com")

7. Conclusion

This topic requires further research. Also, since comparable results can be achieved without eye movements, some research has questioned the theoretical mechanisms behind EMDR (eye movement as a necessary part of EMDR). ("EMDR For Anxiety Disorder and Panic Attacks - AnxietyCentre.com") As many questions remain and more research is needed, EMDR cannot be the first recommendation for the treatment of anxiety disorder (including panic attacks). However, some people may find it helpful when trauma is a component of anxiety disorder, and some aspects of CBT are used in conjunction with EMDR.

Panic disorder (PD) is characterized by recurrent, unexpected panic attacks and hyperarousal symptoms such as palpitations, heart palpitations, chest pain, sweating, tremors or tremors (Frances, 2004). These symptoms are often experienced as catastrophic and can have a major impact on daily life (Frances, 2004). ("Cognitive Behavioral Therapy vs. Eye Movement Desensitization and ...") Moreover, many studies have shown that the quality of life (QOL) of

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Parkinson's patients improves after CBT (Telch et al., 1995; Davidoff et al., 2012). However, a group of patients still need additional treatment after CBT because some patients do not benefit, while others do not make a full recovery or develop other affective disorders (Van Balkom et al, 1996; Bakker et al, 1999).

There are several reasons why EMDR may be useful in the treatment of PD.

- a. *First, panic attacks occur unexpectedly, are experienced as distressing, cause a subjective response of fear or helplessness, and can be considered life-threatening (McNally & Lukach, 1992; Hageraars et al., 2009).*
- b. *Second, there are indications that panic memories in PD resemble traumatic memories as seen in PTSD (Hageraars et al., 2009).*
- c. *Third, there are indications that PD often develops after one or more distressing life events (Faravelli and Pallanti, 1989; Horesh et al., 1997). ("Cognitive Behavioral Therapy vs. Eye Movement ... - Europe PMC")*

More studies are needed for the literature on EMDR therapy.

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